

Meiotic configurations in metaphase I of the "sterile *O. minuta*."

Cells observed (no.)	2n=	a ^a r ^a	Chromosome configuration					Chiasma/cell
			I	II ₁ ^b	II ₂ ^b	III	IV	
15	36		8.60 (5-14)	1.74 (1-4)	10.13 (6-14)	0.93 (0-2)	0.20 (0-1)	24.80 (19-30)

^aa = average, r = range: ^bII₁ = rod bivalents, II₂ = ring bivalents.

Anaphase I of the "sterile *O. minuta*" showing 36 chromosomes, including 11 laggards; two overlapping chromosomes are indicated by the arrow head.

(2n=3x) with 36 chromosomes. Meiotic analysis of its PMCs further indicated its irregular meiosis at different stages. An average of 8.60 univalents, 11.87 bivalents, and a certain amount of multivalents were scored at metaphase I (see table). Meiosis beyond metaphase I was complicated by

other irregularities. Numerous chromosomes were observed to lag at anaphase I and anaphase II (see figure). One chromatid bridge accompanied by a fragment was found at anaphase I. Micronuclei were scored in all quarters. We concluded that this "sterile *O. minuta*" was

a spontaneous hybrid between *O. minuta* and *O. officinalis*, which is classified as a diploid wild rice species (2n=2x=24) containing the CC genome. The sterile population was reported to grow sympatrically with *O. minuta* and *O. officinalis* at the original site.

Numerical analysis of the meiotic configurations in this natural hybrid suggested the best fitting genomic model to be 2:1, with a χ^2 value (relative affinity of the most closely related genomes) of 0.969 and WSSD (weighted sums of squares of differences) of 17.1. This indicates the presence of two closely related genomes (homologous) and one distantly related genome (homoeologous) in the natural hybrid. The two closely related genomes should therefore be the CC genomes derived, respectively, from *O. minuta* (BBCC) and *O. officinalis* (CC). The high frequency of bivalent formation reveals high homology between the CC genomes from the two species. The single distantly related genome should then be the B genome derived from *O. minuta*. The relatively high frequency of multivalents (>1 per cell) and low univalents indicates homoeologous pairing between either the CC genome or the B genome. Furthermore, reciprocal chromosomal translocations in the CC genome of one of the parental species probably causes multivalents to be formed. The chromatid bridge suggests an inversion of a chromosome segment in one of the genomes. ■

Screening RFLP probes for differentiating indicas and japonicas

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Restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) is an effective and reliable tool for classifying the subspecies of *Oryza sativa* L. However, a RFLP survey of the entire rice genome is time-consuming, labor-intensive, and expensive. We report our progress on identifying a set of RFLP probes for differentiating indicas and japonicas.

In our previous RFLP survey of three indica testers and three japonica testers used for screening widely compatible varieties in China, 68 out of 160 probes produced identical hybridization patterns among rice varieties of the same subspecies and different patterns among rice varieties of different subspecies (Zheng et al 1994). Seven established varieties of various origins for both indicas and japonicas were used in RFLP analysis with 68 probes, combined with restriction enzymes *Dra*I, *Eco*RI, *Eco*RV, and *Hind*III. Twenty-one probes regenerated different hybridization patterns between indica and japonica subspecies with at least one enzyme. The majority also regenerated identical patterns within a subspecies. A set of 13 probes for

differentiating subspecies was selected based on Southern blotting performance and chromosome distribution (Qian et al 1995).

To determine the applicability of the indica-japonica differentiation probes, 52 cultivated Asian rice varieties with different geographic distributions were selected and assayed with 100 DNA probes in combination with a single enzyme. The proportions of shared DNA fragments and genetic distances between varieties were quantified according to Nei (1987) based on 184 polymorphic fragments of 65 polymorphic probes. Using the unweighted paired group method with arithmetic mean (Sokal and Michener 1958), the varieties were clearly clustered into two groups.

Indica-japonica discriminate parameters of specific fragments were then computed following the method of Morishima and Gadrinab (1987) with a slight modification (Zhuang et al 1995).

Meanwhile, the 52 varieties were assayed with all the indica-japonica differentiation probes except RG869 and RG684. The discriminate parameters of specific fragments were calculated as $(Di-Dj) = 1$ for indica fragments and $(Di-Dj) = -1$ for japonica fragments. Average discriminate values of specific varieties were calculated and plotted (Fig. 1). Two sets of probes generated similar results, but the degree of indica-japonica differentiation was enlarged by the differentiation probes, as expected.

A similar study was conducted for 20 accessions of *O. rufipogon*. Based on data from the 11 differentiation probes and 113 fragments of 40 DNA probes, average discriminate values of the specific accessions were calculated and plotted (Fig. 2). All followed a general trend. However, the differentiation probes revealed a distinguishable differentiation for indicas and japonicas within *O. rufipogon* while the randomly selected probes did not.

Cited references

- Morishima H, Gadrinad LU. 1987. Are the Asian common wild-rices differentiated into the indica and japonica types? In: Crop exploration and utilization of genetic resources. Proceedings of International Symposium, 6-12 Dec 1986; Chanhua, Taiwan. Taichung District Agricultural Improvement Station. p 11-19.
- Nei M. 1987. Molecular evolutionary genetics. New York: Columbia University Press. p 106-107.
- Qian H-L, Zhuang J-Y, Lin H-X, Lu J. 1985. Identification of a set of RFLP probes for

1. Average indica-japonica discriminate values of 52 rice varieties.

^aBased on data of 11 subspecies differentiation probes.

^bBased on data of 184 fragments of 65 polymorphic probes.

2. Average indica-japonica discriminate values of 20 accessions of *O. rufipogon*.

^aBased on data of 113 fragments of 40 polymorphic probes

^bBased on data of 11 subspecies differentiation probes.

subspecies differentiation in *Oryza sativa* L. Theor. Appl. Genet. 90:878-884.

Sokal RR, Michener CD. 1958. A statistical method for evaluating systematic relationships. Univ. Kansas Sci. Bull. 28:1409-1438.

Zheng K, Qian H, Shen B, Zhuang J, Lin H, Lu J. 1994. RLFP-based phylogenetic analysis of

wide compatibility varieties in *Oryza sativa* L. Theor. Appl. Genet. 88:65-69.

Zhuang J-Y, Qian H-R, Lin H-X, Lu J, Cheng S-H, Ying C-S, Luo L-J, Zhu X-D, Dong F-G, Min S-K, Sun Z-X, Zheng K-L 1995. RFLP-based analysis of the origin and differentiation of *Oryza sativa* L. [in Chinese]. Chin. J. Rice Sci. 9(3): 135-140. ■

Overwintering ability of Dongxiang wild rice in Wuhan District, China

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Dongxiang wild rice is found in Dongxiang County, Jiangxi Province, in the rice belt of central China. The climate is typically continental with extreme minimum temperatures below -10°C . Dongxiang wild rice belongs to *Oryza rufipogon*, which is widely distributed from 18° to 28° $14'$ northern latitude in China.

Wild rice species have been studied to identify useful properties for rice breeding programs, but reports are few on their abilities to overwinter. Therefore, we studied the overwintering ability of Dongxiang wild rice.

In 1993, 14 accessions of *O. rufipogon* were collected from Guangdong, Guangxi,